

THE ESSENCE OF CORRECTING CONFLICTS IN DIFFICULT CHILDREN'S RELATIONSHIPS

Sultanov Raushan Asykbayevna

Turkestan region, Shymkent city, Shymkent University

Dzhumaev Mamanazar Irgashevich

Professor Tashkent State Pedagogical University after Nizami

Abstract: *Where do difficult children come from? "well", he said. The most important reason lies in the upbringing of the family: either the parent is drunk or one of the two is absent. All this affects the behavior of the child, his inner world.*

Some parents with a very low upbringing and culture beat their child, insult him with bad words, and even ask for alms for their child. Here, the child will come tomorrow vindictive, cunning, quarrelsome. Then what will be his fate, what will be his future.

It would not be superfluous to pay attention to one of the words of A. Makarenko. Raising children is an area of our life. Our children are future citizens of our state and the world.

Key words: *difficult child, behavior.*

At the moment when we are crossing the threshold of the XXI century, the problem of "difficult children" still worries us.

As Akhmet Baitursynuly said, "if there are no people who call me a child, where can there be a child who calls me a public". The concept of "difficult children" was used in the problem of education in the 1920s and 1930s. Increasingly, it came into use again in the 1950s and 1960s. Now this issue occupies a real place in science. Of course, many scientists have dealt with this problem, comprehensively studied the character and life of difficult children. Now there are such teenagers.

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Some parents with a very low upbringing and culture beat their child, insult him with bad words, and even ask for alms for their child. Here, the child will come tomorrow vindictive, cunning, quarrelsome. Then what will be his fate, what will be his future.

It would not be superfluous to pay attention to one of the words of A. Makarenko. "Raising children is an area of our life. Our children are future citizens of our state and the world. They are the father and mother of tomorrow, and they will also raise their children. Our children should grow up to be excellent citizens, good fathers, and good mothers. But it doesn't end there either. Our children are our old age. Proper upbringing is our happy old age, it is our tears, it is our fault with other people to the whole country".

Currently, the cause of behavioral disorders is being radically studied, acquired a new character and considered in a socio-psychological, clinical, and criminological context.

Difficulty in behavior is an infinite concept, an irreplaceable psychological feature that is difficult to tolerate educational and socio-psychological influences. Such teenagers, growing up, turn to serious criminal cases. If we analyze and list juvenile delinquency, the list will continue. And if we look at the reasons why children go to the same crime, how difficult children get out, first of all, the child's stomach is full, there are problems with going to school early on the day of the conflict at home, not going. Ways to resolve and resolve these and other issues are proposed by the relevant persons. The child is our future, it is this future generation that will grow and erase the country. The study and observation of the concept of difficulty in behavior and difficult children began to appear in the 1920s and 30s. It was used not in the field of primary science, but in everyday life. Science, which had been used for some time, was abandoned and returned to use in the early 1950s and 60s. Currently, these terms occupy a certain place in scientific dictionaries.

It should be noted that this issue always attracts the attention of sociologists, psychologists, social educators, lawyers, doctors, and teachers and concerns them. The first to

conduct a study on this issue was P.P. Belsky (1917, 1924), who considered minors who deviated from their own behavior. P.P. Belsky devoted 30 years of his time to the study of the inner world of law-breaking children and adolescents. But his theoretical position was not enough. He relies on the theory of L.I. Petrazhitsky (1908), Z. In the course of the study, students were given the opportunity to get acquainted with the history of the Kazakh language and the history of the Kazakh language. On this problem of difficult children, among the above-mentioned scientists, the works of A.S. Makarenko for difficult children and adolescents were included in the Golden fund of Russian pedagogy.

The requirements of the present time are a time of extremely progressive development of knowledge and technology. As you know, the problem of education is also one of the most pressing problems of our time. Because in accordance with the requirements of the time, it is not false that students are more interested in computers and mobile phones. In the family, parents should pay attention to the upbringing of children, keep up to date with information about their daily life, classes, and places of residence, and conduct constant monitoring. Undoubtedly, a violation of the child's behavior pushes parents into difficult situations. In this regard, the role played by parents and the classroom teacher is very important. The content of educational activities has a huge impact on the student.

Currently, it is described in the pedagogical and psychological literature as a strategy for providing assistance. This strategy helps the teacher understand the student's problem, find ways to solve it, and change the situation. The teacher supports the student, pours his mercy on him, in other words, perceives him as his own personality, striving to become the strongest, despite failures and obstacles. Support manifests itself in the following situations: that is, the teacher evaluates not a person, but his actions and, despite his failures as a person, inevitably perceives him as a person. The result of interaction is the student's attitude to himself, self — confidence, the ability to control his behavior, and the desire to form a strong personality. The general structure of the teacher's activity consists of several stages:

- * ability to establish contacts, build a dialogue;
- * identify the student's problems, personal qualities, and obstacles to them;
- * discussion of the issue;
- * providing psychological and pedagogical support.

The technology of interaction communication in solving the problem based on the provision of developmental assistance provides the following techniques of teacher behavior:

- * show interest in the conversation, learn to look directly at its face and listen;
- * tell everything in the game, be able to remain calm, try to understand the student's condition;
- * ability to express your sympathy;
- * ability to get the necessary information and ask questions aimed at understanding everything;
- * try to understand the other person's problem and find a solution to it;
- * encourage you to make decisions that contribute to solving the problem rather than just consulting.

Such conditions are provided for the classroom teacher's interview with the student. It is based on the view of a person as a person who strives for self-development, and the view of a student as a person who is developing, able to help students.

The family is the cradle of personality formation. "If you want to form a citizen, correct your cradle", the great scientist M.Auezov has been directing since time immemorial [3]. In the family, the foundation of interpersonal relationships is laid, labor and social orientation is formed, which is sufficient for the entire life. As you know, many problems in the family, which are solved in a simple and easy way, fall into a difficult state in adulthood. Indeed, it is known that the beginning of education is in the cradle, in the family. A child who drinks his mother's milk in the cradle, listens to lullabies, feels family kindness, and improves his working abilities is the future of our sovereign country.

Parents in today's families do not have the same abilities and opportunities to organize the upbringing of children in accordance with the requirements of the time. The fact that one of

the Kazakh intellectuals M.Zhumabayev said that "the goal of education is not to make a child look like the teacher himself, but to make the future worthy of his time" proves the great responsibility of parents in raising children. Of course, the family, through its independent actions, shows weakness in solving large-scale problems in the field of Education. For this purpose, it is very important to strengthen the mutual cooperation between the family and the school. And since education is a social phenomenon, it cannot be organized outside the requirements of society. At the same time, the Trinity Union: Schools, families and public institutions should find a harmony of continuity and cooperation in work. Today, the progress of family education was observed from a two-way perspective. The first is that the family is very eager to cooperate with the school. Here, parents transfer their children to study at the best school, so that they receive a high-quality education and comprehensive development. "I don't know", he said. As a result of mutual cooperation between the school and the family, various assistance to the pedagogical activities of the school is provided by parents, in particular, sponsorship, exchange of educational experience, introduction of professional activities, etc. Let's be a country and a society to ensure that the Kazakh people do not have difficult children to raise!

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KOMPETENSIYAVIY YONDASHUV ASOSIDA BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF TARBIYA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISH

Saidova Gavhar Ergashovna

Buxoro davlat pedagogika instituti "Boshlang'ich ta'lim" kafedrasida dotsenti

Annotatsiya: Boshlang'ich ta'limda tarbiya darslarida kompetensiyaviy yondashuv yo'llari, boshlang'ich sinflarda foydalanish mumkin bo'lgan innovatsion texnologiyalarning didaktik tamoyillari, boshlang'ich sinflarda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyati, tarbiya fani dars jarayonida talabalarning mehnat tarbiyasini shakllantirishda innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanishning muhim jihatlari haqida ma'lumot berish.

Kalit so'zlar: intarfaol metodlar, innovatsiya, pedagogik texnologiya, didaktik tamoyillar, innovatsion texnologiya, ta'lim-tarbiya, didaktik vosita, ta'lim samaradorligi.

Tarbiya fani asosida quyidagi kompetensiyalar shakllantiriladi:

Ma'naviy-axloqiy madaniyatlik kompetensiyasi: odob-axloq (kiyinish, muomala, muloqot, jamoat joylarida o'zini tutish) madaniyatiga ega bo'lishi hamda milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni anglash va hurmat qilish, oila, jamiyat, Vatan oldidagi burch hamda mas'uliyatni anglashi va ularga rioya qilishi, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni, milliy-madaniy an'analar, urfodatlar, marosimlarga nisbatan hurmat bilan munosabatda bo'lishi, jamoatchilik ishlarida faol bo'lishi.

Mafkuraviy immunitetga ega bo'lish kompetensiyasi: yaxshi va yomon xatti-harakatlarni farqlay olishi, ularga nisbatan fikrini bayon eta olishi; yon-atrofida bo'layotgan voqea-hodisalarga munosabat bildira olishi, ilmlilik insonning yuksak ziynati ekanini anglay boshlash ko'nikmalariga ega bo'lishi lozim.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'rganish va bilish darajasi, faolligi, dunyoqarashi va fikr olish qobiliyatining rivojlanganligiga ko'ra shartli ravishda ikki bosqichga ya'ni 1-2-sinf o'quvchilarida ijtimoiy-huquqiy me'yorlarni o'rganish va ushbu tushunchalar haqidagi bilimlarga ega bo'lish hamda 3-4-sinfda egallagan kompetensiyalarni hayotda qo'llay olish ko'nikmasini shakllantirish inobatga olinishi lozim.

Tarbiya faniga oid kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish jarayonida dars jarayonida